

Relationship Between Healthy Organisational Resources and Organisational Citizenship Behaviour of Employees in an Institution of Higher Education

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Abstract

Background: Healthy organisational practices proposed by the Healthy and Resilient Organisations (HERO) model were used as independent variables to analyse people management in the organisation. These practices influenced workers' health and well-being, measured by engagement as a positive practice and burnout as a negative practice.

Objective: This study seeks to establish the relationship between healthy organisational resources and organisational citizenship behaviour in a Higher Education Institution (HEI).

Methodology: A quantitative correlational study was conducted in a sample of 111 employees from a higher education institution in the city of Manizales, Colombia, using convenience sampling. Data were collected through two questionnaires: the first, based on the HERO model of Healthy Organisational Resources and the second, the Organisational Citizenship Behaviour Scale among co-workers. The data were analysed using the open-source software JASP.

Results: A significant positive correlation is observed at moderate to strong levels. The positive relationship between supportive climate and altruism stands out, with a correlation coefficient of 0.698. In addition, transformational leadership communication shows a strong positive correlation with altruism, with a correlation coefficient of 0.660. A moderate to strong positive correlation is also observed between teamwork and altruism, with a correlation coefficient of 0.608. Additional correlations were identified, including a moderate to strong correlation between teamwork and

responsibility, with a correlation coefficient of 0.620, and, finally, a positive correlation between supportive climate and responsibility, with a correlation coefficient of 0.619.

Conclusion: A significant positive relationship exists between organisational resources: supportive climate, teamwork and transformative communication and organisational citizenship behaviours: altruism and organisational awareness.

Unique Contribution: This study has provided empirical evidence that can guide human resource management and prevention and promotion policies and practices to improve working life quality by fostering a culture of positive organisational citizenship.

Keywords: Organisation, higher education institution, healthy organisations, organisational resilience, work psychology.

Introduction

In the current context of higher education organisations, effective management of organisational resources and fostering organisational citizenship behaviour are critical to the sustainability and success of institutions. Organisational resources encompass both tangible and intangible assets, such as work climate, leadership, employee well-being, and organisational culture (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). These elements form the foundation on which healthy work environments are built in any organisation, as employees respond positively to practices and resources that not only meet their needs but also promote their development and well-being.

On the other hand, organisational citizenship behaviours, defined as those voluntary behaviours or willingness of employees to engage beyond their formal roles, emerge as a determining factor in building healthy and productive work environments. These behaviours include cooperation, altruism and commitment to institutional goals (Organ et al., 2006). Organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is an important aspect that should be the subject of organisational attention and study because of its impact on job satisfaction (Soetjijpto et al., 2021) and on generating competitive advantage in a business environment (Organ et al., 2006). Studies have argued that employees who identify with an organisation's values and norms demonstrate more OCB.

After examining the terms individually, studies of the relationship between organisational resources and organisational citizenship behaviour are explored, it should be noted that at the time of the search no evidence of studies analysing this relationship in higher education institutions was found. However, there have been studies that analyse the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behaviour with variables such as Work Engagement, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment, variables that stand out as critical factors for an effective operation of organizations, as it involves the promotion of a positive work environment and the active contribution of employees beyond their formal roles (Hu, 2022; Abbasi, et al., 2022). Other studies have analysed the relationship between healthy organisational practices proposed by the HERO model and people management in the organisation (Acuña-Hormazabal et al., 2021), the results showed that practices influence the health and well-being of workers.

In this sense, the purpose of this study was to establish the relationship between healthy organisational resources and organisational citizenship behaviour in a higher education institution.

Literature review and hypothesis development

Theory of organisational demands and resources

Organisational demands theory within the field of organisational psychology seeks to understand how the characteristics of a job and the work environment can affect employee well-being and performance, and to identify individual and group resources. This theory is based on the idea that workers face both physical and psychological demands in their jobs, and how these demands are perceived and addressed affects their job satisfaction, health and performance (Bakker & Demerouti, 2013).

Work resources: refer to physical, social and psychological aspects that help employees cope with work demands, maintain well-being and performance. These can be personal (skills and capabilities) and organisational (social support, training and access to appropriate technology). These resources contribute to employee satisfaction, promoting motivation, commitment and psychological well-being and can originate from within the organisation, with appropriate organisational practices and management support. The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model assumes that resources play a crucial role in preventing health deterioration and enhancing motivation (Bakker & Demerouti, 2013).

Job demands: These are the physical and psychological aspects of the job that require effort and energy on the part of the employee. These may include workload, time pressure, task complexity, degree of autonomy, and responsibility, among other factors (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008). When work demands exceed available resources, employees may experience stress and burnout. On the other hand, if resources exceed demands, there may be a positive impact on well-being and productivity (Salanova et al., 2019).

Theory of healthy and resilient organisations

Organisational health refers to positive aspects of the work environment that contribute to the well-being and health of employees. These may include dimensions such as social support, positive leadership, job autonomy, effective communication and work-life balance, among others. Healthy organisations have undergone continuous development and evolution, enriched by the valuable contributions of various researchers and academics in the field, including Marisa Salanova, who has conducted important research and proposed the HERO model (Salanova, 2009).

Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB)

In the book *The good soldier's syndrome* (1988), Organ defined the concept of organisational citizenship behaviours as 'discretionary individual behaviour, not directly or explicitly recognised by the formal reward system, and which on the whole promotes the efficient and effective functioning of the organisation' (Organ et al., 2006, P3). According to the literature, several organisational factors can positively influence OCB, including an ethical organisational work environment (Fein et al., 2023).

The adoption of organisational citizenship behaviours represents a voluntary commitment by the employees, rather than an obligation stipulated in employment contracts. These actions not only have the potential to stimulate employees' commitment to the company, but also to strengthen the organisational culture and enrich the work environment, as several studies have shown (Abbasi et al., 2022; Abbasi et al., 2022). On the other hand, OCB has positive impacts on employees by

enhancing their sense of self-efficacy (Choong & Ng, 2023) and personal reputation and job satisfaction (Dai et al., 2022).

Research hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant relationship between healthy organisational resources and the dimensions of organisational citizenship behaviour: altruism, conscientiousness, civic participation, sportsmanship and courtesy of employees in an institution of higher education.

H1: There is a significant relationship between healthy organisational resources and the dimensions of organisational citizenship behaviour: altruism, conscientiousness, civic participation, sportsmanship and courtesy of employees in an institution of higher education.

Methodology

The present research is framed in a quantitative approach study, it was selected for its ability to collect and analyse numerical data, allowing the identification of patterns, testing hypotheses, and establishing relationships between variables in an objective and systematic way of organisational phenomena. Its design is observational with a correlational scope; this design was selected because it allows the study of phenomena in their natural context without manipulating variables, which is suitable for investigating existing associations (Kumar et al., 2023). A correlational scope was adopted to examine the relationship between two or more variables, allowing for the identification of significant associations without inferring causality

The study population was 402 employees, including teaching and administrative staff of a private higher education institution in the city of Manizales, department of Caldas, Colombia. Purposive sampling was used, selected for convenience and accessibility, considering the location and availability of the researcher for data collection. After applying exclusion criteria, the sample was reduced to 180 employees. Of these, 111 employees responded, representing 61.6 % of the selected sample. Data collection took place between June and July 2023, following the guidelines of the Institution's Ethics Committee. The instruments were applied virtually, with the support of the institution's quality department, which distributed the link of the questionnaire to the selected employees via institutional mail.

Two instruments were used for data collection:

Healthy Organisational Resources Questionnaire: consists of 11 single items, included in the battery of instruments of the HERO model (Salanova et al., 2012). The following dimensions were assessed: autonomy, feedback, supportive climate, teamwork, coordination, transformational leadership vision, transformational leadership-inspirational communication-leadership, transformational intellectual leadership stimulation, transformational leadership support, transformational personal leadership recognition, healthy organisational practices, transformational leadership support, transformational leadership recognition.

A reliability analysis of the instrument was carried out for the study using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, obtaining a value of 0.923, this result indicates a high internal consistency of the instrument which validated its use for data collection. This value is similar to the one by (Salanova et al. 2012) who reported an average reliability of 0.811.

Employee organisational citizenship behaviour scale: The instrument proposed by (Rodríguez et al. 2013) was selected. This choice is based on its strong relevance and validity in relation to the objectives and scope of the research, as this instrument has been previously validated in similar studies and has proven to be an effective tool to collect the necessary data accurately and reliably. The dimensions addressed in the instrument are the following: altruism, responsibility, civic participation, sportsmanship, civility and courtesy; each dimension containing 15 items which are scored on a Likert scale. A reliability analysis of the instrument was conducted using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, yielding a value of 0.929, which validated its use for data collection. This result aligns with that reported by Rodríguez et al. (2013), who obtained a coefficient of 0.802, highlighting the consistency of the findings in both studies.

Data analysis was performed using the free software JASP, a free and open-source statistical analysis programme supported by the University of Amsterdam.

Results

The study covered a sample of 111 contributors with an average age of 43 years. The most represented age group was in the range of 36 to 45 years, accounting for 35% of the participants, followed by the range of 46 to 55 years, which represented 30%. Subsequently, the group of the range between 26 and 35 years makes up 20% of the sample, indicating that the largest number of participants are in the adult age group, according to the age classification scale of the Ministry of Health and Social Protection.

In addition, the majority of the population studied is female, representing 60% of the total. In terms of marital status, the married category predominates, with 41% of the participants. In terms of educational level, people with a master's degree are predominant, accounting for 41%. In terms of length of service in the labour market, the range of 1 to 5 years stands out, with a share of 32%.

Spearman correlation

To achieve the objective, a table was created detailing the dimensions that showed a relationship between them, using Spearman's correlation coefficient for non-parametric statistical tests (Mendivelso, 2022).

Table 1.

Spearman's correlation analysis between ECCOCT and Organizational Resources

Dimensions of ECCOCT	Dimensions of Healthy organizational Resources	I1	I2	Spearman		
				rho	p	Significance
Altruism	Supportive environment	P2	P3	0.770	< .001	***
		P1	P3	0.701	< .001	***
		P3	P3	0.694	< .001	***
Altruism	Transformational leadership-inspirational (interpersonal)- leadership communication	P2	P7	0.660	< .001	***

Awareness	Teamwork	P4	P4	0.620	< .001	***
	Supportive environment	P5	P3	0.620	< .001	***
		P4	P3	0.617	< .001	***
Altruism	Transformational leadership- inspirational (interpersonal)- leadership communication	P3	P7	0.612	< .001	***
Civic participation	Teamwork	P2	P4	0.608	< .001	***
	Supportive environment	P9	P3	0.599	< .001	***
Altruism	Transformational leadership- inspirational (interpersonal)- leadership communication	P1	P7	0.574	< .001	***
Awareness	Teamwork	P5	P4	0.571	< .001	***
Civic participation	Healthy organisational practices	I1P9	I2P11	0.565	< .001	***
Altruism	Healthy organisational practices	I1P1	I2P11	0.564	< .001	***
Awareness	Transformational leadership- inspirational (interpersonal)- leadership communication	I1P4	I2P7	0.560	< .001	***
Altruism	Autonomy	I1P3	I2P1	0.559	< .001	***

Note. Own elaboration. Correlation analysis was carried out with the JASP software

Table 1 shows that the p-value is (< .001) and the significance (***) is high in all dimensions, so the null hypothesis is rejected. The alternative hypothesis is accepted, which would suggest that the presence of healthy organisational resources has a significant impact on employees' willingness to engage in organisational citizenship behaviours in the HEI.

For this reason, the research has established a correlation threshold using Spearman's coefficient, which is set at a value higher than 0.6. This threshold indicates a preference for moderate to strong correlations, considering that all dimensions exhibited positive correlations at moderate to strong levels. This ranking is based on Spearman's correlation interpretation scale.

Figure 1.

Dimensions between healthy organizational resources and ECCOCT with the highest correlation value.

Note. Prepared by the authors

Figure 1 shows a significant positive correlation at moderate to strong levels. In particular, the positive relationship between supportive climate and altruism stands out, evidenced by a correlation coefficient rho of 0.698. Additionally, transformational leadership communication exhibits a strong positive correlation with altruism, with a correlation coefficient of 0.660. A moderate to strong positive correlation is also observed between teamwork and altruism, with a rho of 0.608. Additional correlations were identified, including a moderate to strong correlation between teamwork and conscientiousness, with a rho of 0.620, and, finally, a positive correlation between supportive climate and conscientiousness, with a rho of 0.619.

Discussion

Significant correlations were found in certain dimensions when the relationship between healthy organisational resources and employees' organisational citizenship behaviour in the HEI was examined.

First, a positive association was found between the dimensions of supportive climate and altruism, with a rho correlation of 0.698, as well as a strong positive correlation between the dimensions of transformational leadership communication and altruism, represented by a rho of 0.660. These findings suggest a relevant connection between the availability of organisational resources and employees' willingness to contribute proactively to the work environment. For some authors, resources are the strongest predictors of work engagement (Mazzetti et al., 2023).

In addition, a moderate to strong positive correlation was observed between the dimensions of teamwork and altruism, with a correlation coefficient (rho) of 0.608. A moderate to strong positive correlation was also observed between the dimensions of teamwork and responsibility, with a rho of 0.620. Furthermore, a positive correlation was observed between the supportive climate and responsibility, with a rho of 0.619.

Healthy organisational resources such as supportive climate, communication based on transformational leadership and teamwork are positively correlated with increased altruistic

behaviour of employees. Additionally, the results showed that teamwork and a supportive climate are associated with higher levels of accountability among employees. In this sense, the approach that OCB is influenced not only by external environmental factors, but also by individual values and internal organisational motives, is corroborated

These additional correlations reinforce the validity of the alternative hypothesis, supporting the idea that the presence of healthy organisational resources is positively related to a higher level of organisational citizenship among employees. That is, increased organisational resources could improve the conditions for employees to display supportive behaviours towards others in their tasks or in the face of an educational institution-related problem that transcends the demands of the job.

Considering the literature review conducted for this study, did not identify previous literature that directly supports the relationship between healthy organisational resources and increased employee organisational citizenship behaviour; it did find studies that explore the connection between organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational resources with other variables that also explore their organisational implications.

Consistent with this, a longitudinal study by van der Meer et al. (2022) found that job resources, such as autonomy, task variety and social support, positively influence employee well-being. Other studies have found that employees who identify with the organisation and are willing to establish a long-term relationship depend, to a large extent, on the recognition and trustworthiness they perceive in their leader. According to Yang and Tsai (2023), when employees feel they can benefit from organisational behaviour or leadership, they tend to respond with positive attitudes and actions towards the organisation and its leaders. The supportive climate provided by immediate supervisors and co-workers also has a long-term effect on work engagement. A study by Abbasi et al. (2022) confirms the mediating role of organisational citizenship behaviour in the relationship between organisational justice and workplace deviance, highlighting its relevance, especially in higher education.

This underlines that organisational citizenship behaviour plays a key role in the efficient performance of assigned functions. Faculty members who have positive perceptions of organisational citizenship behaviours suggest that they add greater value to the university by volunteering to help new faculty and dedicating their personal time to improving the performance of their students and the organisation (Bastian & Widodo, 2022). In addition, some academic studies have highlighted the relationship between OCB and the employee, finding that OCB has a significant and positive impact on the intention to stay with the organisation, which is key to reducing teacher turnover levels.

These findings also suggest the importance for higher education institutions to promote healthy organisational resources, such as supportive climate, communicative leadership and teamwork, in their work environment in order to cultivate positive citizenship behaviour within the organisation, as according to (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018), the work resource package is an effective intervention strategy designed to boost co-worker support and work engagement. This approach also enhances

productivity and fosters healthy and resilient work teams that are able to adapt effectively to change (Bakker & Demerouti, 2013; Salanova, 2009).

Further research could examine how these organisational resources, by fostering organisational citizenship among employees, can influence customer satisfaction. Understanding this relationship would help organisations improve the customer experience and, ultimately, their competitive position in the marketplace. In summary, these lines of research offer a broad field for advancing knowledge in organisational management and work psychology in the Colombian context.

Conclusion

First, the high Cronbach's α coefficients show remarkable internal consistency, confirming the reliability of the instruments used to identify healthy organisational resources and determine organisational citizenship behaviour. This support reinforces their ability to provide accurate and consistent measurements. Therefore, these findings reinforce the validity of the results in the context of the theoretical framework and previous research.

Second, the existence of healthy organisational resources has a significant impact on the organisational citizenship behaviour of HEI employees. Therefore, work environments that foster healthy aspects such as a supportive climate, teamwork and leadership have the potential to stimulate employees' engagement in behaviours that benefit the organisation.

Third, these findings have significant implications for management and policy-making in higher education institutions. The promotion of healthy organisational resources is presented as an effective strategy for cultivating an environment where employees are motivated to adopt behaviours that transcend conventional work expectations. In this way, it fosters a culture of organisational citizenship that has a positive impact on the overall benefit of the institution.

Finally, healthy organisational and organisational citizenship behaviour substantially strengthens the occupational health and safety management system. This strengthening translates into positive results for customer service, thus contributing to the strengthening of the quality management system.

Practical Implications of the Results

This research has significant implications for management and policy-making in higher education institutions. The promotion of healthy organisational resources emerges as an effective strategy for cultivating an environment where employees are motivated to engage in behaviours that go beyond conventional work expectations. In this way, a culture of organisational citizenship is fostered that has a positive impact on the overall benefit of the institution.

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